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A framework to generate local spectral skies for spectral daylight simulations

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Abstract. Spectral daylight simulations are becoming increasingly important in predicting non-visual responses to light and more accurate daylight colour and temporal patterns. However, the availability of locally measured spectral sky data is limited and current spectral sky models do not capture the local colour variability of skies. This paper presents a novel framework for generating high-accuracy, location-specific spectral sky data using typically measured atmospheric data at meteorological stations as inputs to physics-based radiative transfer programs like libRadtran. A comparison of measured and simulated data across the year demonstrates that using location-specific atmospheric profiles leads to significantly more accurate predictions of irradiances, spectral global and direct irradiances, and better captures the variability of clear skies regarding colour accuracy and appearance than simulations with default settings.

1. Introduction

Lighting simulation tools have historically relied on luminance-based sky models, such as Commission Internationale de l'Eclairage (CIE) [1] or Perez all-weather skies [2], which lack spectral and colorimetric information. While these models provide a good estimate of daylight availability and visual contrasts, it cannot help evaluate non-visual impacts or colour renditions of daylight. The colour accuracy of simulations and colour appearance of daylight renders are also significantly affected with luminance based, non-spectral sky models [3].

Currently, few lighting simulation tools can perform spectral daylight simulations and incorporate sky models with spectral daylight information. The multi-spectral lighting plugin Lark [5] generates a sky model using user-defined Correlated Colour Temperature (CCT) or global spectral irradiance of skies with luminance distribution from Perez all weather or CIE sky model. The plugins gendaylit [6] and OWL [7] for Radiance utilize a luminance-based CCT model [8,9], while the software ALFA [10] uses libRadtran, a physics-based radiative transfer library [11], to pre-compute spectral radiances of the sky. ALFA's sky model is currently the only one that can capture the spatial-spectral variability of direct sun and diffuse sky radiation across the sky dome [3, 4]. This is because libRadtran relies on a direct solar radiative transfer through the atmosphere and atmospheric input data.

Several studies have shown there are location-specific differences in the colour and spectrum of daylight [13-15]. For further development of spectral models for the lighting field, it is suggested that the variability of the different shades of blue and the colour of sunlight and daylight be represented [4].

However, measuring spectral sun and sky data requires expensive instrumentation and maintenance and only a few locations worldwide record spectral measurements of the sky dome.

Hence, the paper proposes a framework for generating location-specific spectral daylight and sunlight using libRadtran with typically measured atmospheric parameters like water vapour, pressure, ozone, and aerosol. The framework is demonstrated for the location of Lindenberg, Germany, using measurements from the Meteorological Observatory Lindenberg (LIN). Irradiances, global and direct spectral irradiances simulated with libRadtran using a local profile (simulation set-up with location-specific atmospheric inputs) and a default profile (simulation set-up with no modifications to atmospheric inputs) are compared with measured data. The proposed framework can be used to generate local spectral clear skies for use in ALFA or the generated spectral power distributions (SPDs) can be used as an input for Lark.

2. Methodology

2.1. Atmospheric parameters affecting the visual spectrum of solar radiation

The atmosphere is mostly transparent in the visible spectral band (wavelength in the range of 380-780 nm) [16] except for isolated gas absorption bands (O_2 above 750 nm) or weak absorption continua (for example, O_3 centred at 550 nm). Water vapour, an abundant atmospheric constituent, has a significant absorption band at the longwave end of the visible spectral band. Other atmospheric components that affect the visible spectral band, especially in clear sky conditions, are the aerosols (due to absorption and scattering) and air molecules (most abundant are N_2 and O_2) due to Rayleigh scattering. The Rayleigh scattering is proportional to the total amount of air and quantified by pressure (p in mbar). Aerosol extinction is quantified by Aerosol Optical Depth (AOD) at a given wavelength and Single Scattering Albedo (SSA). An SSA = 0 represents a completely absorbing aerosol mixture, and SSA = 1 represents a purely scattering mixture. AOD is monochromatic, but for spherical particles, the spectrum of the AOD can be computed with the Ångström equation using the two Ångström's exponents: α and β .

Therefore, to set up a radiative transfer simulation for a cloud-free atmosphere with a local atmospheric profile, the p , α and β , and SSA are specified. This setup is to obtain the spectrum of solar radiation on the ground level. Additional parameters required to increase precision are the water vapour amount represented as Precipitable Water Vapour (PWV in mm) and the total NO_2 column and total O_3 column (TOC), both in Dobson Units (DU).

2.2. Description of local and default profile set-ups in libRadtran

2.2.1. Atmospheric profile. Defining the atmosphere is an essential component of running a radiative transfer simulation like libRadtran. An atmosphere file usually contains profiles of pressure, temperature, air density, and concentrations of O_3 , O_2 , CO_2 , water vapour and NO_2 [11]. The U.S. Air Force Geophysics Laboratory (AFGL) Atmospheric Constituent Profiles [17] were used for both the local and default simulation set-ups. Specifically, the AFGL midlatitude summer profile was used since the location is based in Europe. ALFA also uses the same AFGL profile for precomputing skies for worldwide locations. For the rest of the paper, the local and default libRadtran simulations and set-ups will be referred to as libLOC and libDEF.

For the libLOC setup, user-defined measurements of the total columnar amounts of p , TOC, NO_2 , and PWV are used to modify the atmospheric profile, while maintaining the relative vertical definition of the AFGL profile. In contrast, default values are used for libDEF setups without modifications.

2.2.2. Aerosol properties. The aerosol properties for the libLOC and libDEF are defined by the aerosol model proposed by [18], which is initiated by the *aerosol_default* command in libRadtran. The default aerosol properties are a 'rural type' aerosol, defined for spring-summer conditions and a visibility of 50 km [11]. The default aerosol properties for the libLOC simulation are modified with user-defined

measured values of SSA, α , and β . In the libDEF simulation set-up, the default aerosol properties are only modified to an 'urban type' aerosol property based on ALFA's clear sky set-up (for all locations worldwide).

2.2.3. Other common set-up parameters for local and default profile in libRadtran. For both libLOC and libDEF simulations, the location details are specified by altitude (130 m), latitude ($52^\circ 12' N$), and longitude ($14^\circ 07' E$) for LIN. The Solar Zenith Angle (SZA) and the day of the year are used to define the day and time for the simulations. LibRadtran's default DISORT solver [19] is used as the radiative transfer equation solver. The extraterrestrial solar spectrum is defined using Kurudz [20] 1.0 nm resolution covering the complete solar spectral range (250 nm to 10,000 nm).

2.3. Description of the measurement site at Lindenberg (LIN)

The Meteorological Observatory Lindenberg - Richard Aßmann Observatory is a supersite for meteorological measurements, located in Lindenberg (Tauche), a rural site in Brandenburg, 60 km southeast of Berlin. It is affiliated with the German Meteorological Service DWD.

The supersite provides all the necessary atmospheric parameters required for libLOC input set-ups. A sun photometer is used to measure spectral AOD (therefore α and β) and SSA, a global positioning system for PWV, and a UV spectrometer for TOC. In addition to these parameters, they use pyranometers to measure the downward global irradiances, pyranometers with shadower for the diffuse irradiances and pyrheliometer for measuring direct normal irradiances. The site also measures global spectral and direct solar spectral irradiances using spectroradiometers. Therefore, the framework proposed in this paper can be effectively tested at LIN with the supersite, where both the atmospheric parameters needed for input and the measurement dataset required for evaluation are available.

2.4. Description of clear sky dataset

A cloud-free, clear-sky dataset of 101 distinct timestamps throughout the year was selected. Specific dates were chosen such that three criteria were met (1) availability of a complete set of atmospheric input parameters, (2) availability of both spectral and broadband measurements, and (3) measurements representing every season. The measurement dataset spans from February to September, with SZA ranging from 41 to 78 degrees. The p ranges from 994 to 1021 mbar, TOC ranges from 275 to 424 DU, PWV 5.7 to 29 mm, AOD at 500 nm wavelength from 0.05 to 0.31 and SSA from 0.78 to 0.99.

A subset of this dataset, with 39 distinct timestamps, is used for the direct solar spectral irradiance comparisons due to the unavailability of these specific measurements for the rest of the dates. This measurement dataset is for June, August and September, with SZA ranging from 43 to 75 degrees.

3. Evaluation of simulations with measurement I: error analysis

Since LIN has broadband and spectral measurement data, we evaluate two sets of simulations using libLOC and libDEF against measured data, the first set includes the broadband, while the second set includes spectral comparisons.

3.1. Comparison of broadband irradiances

LibRadtran simulations were set up with libLOC and libDEF profile to obtain downward global irradiances, diffuse irradiances and direct normal irradiances for the wavelength range 285 nm to 4000 nm for the 101 timestamps described in Section 2.4. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) and Mean Absolute Percentage Difference (MAPD) were calculated between the measured and simulated values, and the results are presented in Table 1. For the integrated simulations, libLOC outperforms libDEF.

3.2. Comparison of spectral irradiances

Libradtran simulations were conducted with libLOC and libDEF to obtain global spectral and direct solar spectral irradiances in the visible wavelength range (380 to 780 nm) for 101 and 39 timestamps, respectively. Table 2 shows the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), and MAE calculated between the

simulated and measured values. The results indicate that the libDEF setup produces significantly larger errors when simulating direct solar spectral irradiance than global spectral irradiance. libLOC produces lower RMSE and MAE values for both spectral irradiance simulations.

Table 1. comparison of Mean Absolute Error (MAE in W/sqm) and Mean Absolute Percentage Difference (MAPD in %) for broadband irradiances

	MAE (libLOC)	MAE (libDEF)	MAPD (libLOC)	MAPD (libDEF)
Downward global	3.6	43.7	0.76	9.6
Diffuse	3.4	15.6	3.9	18.8
Direct normal	4.7	50.4	1.2	13.2

Table 2. comparison of Root Mean Square Error (RMSE in W/sqm.nm) and Mean Absolute Error (MAE in W/sqm.nm) for spectral irradiances

	RMSE (libLOC)	RMSE (libDEF)	MAE (libLOC)	MAE (libDEF)
Global spectral	0.03	0.05	0.02	0.04
Direct solar spectral	0.05	0.19	0.03	0.16

To assess the significance of the difference in RMSE between libLOC (0.03) and libDEF (0.05) for the global spectral irradiance, the RMSE between upper and lower bounds of measurement uncertainty was calculated, with a $\pm 2.4\%$ measurement uncertainty derived from the calibration certificate for spectral irradiances of the JETI specbos 1201 spectroradiometer (wavelength range of 380 to 780 nm and 1 nm resolution). Figure 1 shows that the mean and range of libLOC RMSE errors are within the RMSE uncertainty bounds of the global spectral irradiance measurement data, indicating high accuracy of SPDs generated with a libLOC setup.

Figure 1. Comparison of global spectral irradiance (sglo): RMSE (in W/sqm.nm) distribution of libDEF, libLOC and measured bounds

Figure 2. Comparison of global spectral irradiance (sglo): RMSE (in W/sqm.nm) distribution of libLOC and libDEF in RGB wavelength bins

4. Evaluation of simulation with measurement II: for application

4.1. Comparison in red, green and blue (RGB) channels

Radiance-based spectral lighting simulation tools, such as Lark and ALFA, generate images using a multiple colour channel simulation. Lark performs 3 or 9-channel simulations, while ALFA performs 81-channel simulations [3]. The wavelength interval used in Radiance and Lark for standard RGB

imagery is 380-498 nm (B), 498-586 nm (G), and 586-780 nm (R) [5]. We use these wavelength bins as a reference to highlight potential errors in the RGB 3-channel simulations when using libLOC or libDEF SPDs as a daylight source. The evaluation in Figure 2 shows the potential of large errors in the red and green channel simulations when using libDEF SPD, with smaller errors when using libLOC's SPD. Error difference between them is smaller in the blue wavelength region.

4.2. Comparison of CCT

The CCT of measured and simulated global spectral irradiance was calculated using the Robertson method [21], with results presented in Kelvins (K). A scatterplot with a linear regression line was used to investigate the correlation between the CCT of libLOC and libDEF simulations and measured CCT (Figure 3). Pearson's coefficient (r) showed a strong and positive correlation for libLOC ($r = 0.90$) and a moderate correlation for libDEF ($r = 0.53$). The RMSE for libLOC's CCT was lower (50 K) than for libDEF (70 K), and libLOC slightly overpredicted CCT while libDEF underpredicted CCT, as demonstrated by the Mean Bias Error (MBE) calculations (Figure 3): libLOC had an MBE of 36 K and libDEF had an MBE of -20 K.

Figure 3. Computed CCT (in K) for measured global spectral irradiance versus libLOC and libDEF simulated global spectral irradiance, also reflected in Pearson's coefficient r , RMSE and Mean Bias Error (MBE)

4.3. Comparison of Melanopic Equivalent Daylight Illuminance (MEDI)

To assess the impact of libLOC and libDEF SPDs on non-image forming effects, MEDI was calculated for both simulated and measured global spectral irradiance using the melanopic spectral sensitivity and the CIE S 026/2018 standard [22]. The correlation between simulated and measured MEDI was investigated and visualized in Figure 4, showing a strong positive correlation for both libLOC ($r = 0.997$) and libDEF ($r = 0.992$). However, libLOC slightly overpredicted MEDI with a comparatively lower RMSE, while libDEF largely underpredicted MEDI with a higher RMSE.

Figure 4. Computed MEDI (in lux) for measured global spectral irradiance versus libLOC and libDEF simulated global spectral irradiance

5. Conclusion

This paper presents a framework for generating high-accuracy, location-specific spectral sunlight and daylight using commonly measured atmospheric parameters in radiative transfer simulations like libRadtran. The framework can generate SPDs for spectral simulation tools like Lark or be adapted for use in ALFA. We evaluated the framework for Lindenberg, near Berlin, Germany, with measured direct, diffuse and global irradiances and global and direct solar spectral irradiances. The results demonstrate that location-specific set-up, libLOC, produces irradiances and SPDs with lower errors and within the range of uncertainty percentages of spectroradiometers compared to default set-ups (libDEF) in libRadtran. In terms of colour accuracy, libLOC outperforms libDEF, with lower errors observed in red and green colour channels for radiance-based spectral simulation methods. Additionally, a strong positive linear relationship exists between the computed CCTs of libLOC and the measured spectral global irradiances. However, both libLOC and libDEF exhibit a strong positive linear relationship with measured non-image forming metrics MEDI, with libDEF tending to underestimate MEDI. Future work is valuable and necessary to evaluate the framework in different locations, under varying sky conditions and for spectral sky radiances.

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References

- [1] Spatial Distribution of Daylight. 1996 CIE General Standard Sky CIE S003/ISO 15469.
- [2] Perez, R., Seals, R., & Michalsky, J. (1993). All-weather model for sky luminance distribution. *Solar energy*, 50(3), 235-245.
- [3] Balakrishnan P and Jakubiec A 2019 A Spectral Rendering with Daylight: A Comparison of Two Spectral Daylight Simulation Platforms Building Simulation Conference
- [4] Inanici M, Abboushi B and Safranek S 2022 Evaluation of sky spectra and sky models in daylighting simulations *Lighting Research & Technology* 147715352211034
- [5] Inanici M, Brennan M and Clark E 2015 Spectral Lighting Simulations: Computing Circadian Light Building Simulation Conference
- [6] gendaylit. A colored sky description based on the model from A. Diakite. Accessed 24 April 2023, from <https://www.radiance-online.org/learning/documentation/manual-pages/pdfs/gendaylit.pdf>
- [7] Maskarenj M, Deroisy B and Altomonte S 2022 A new tool and workflow for the simulation of the non-image forming effects of light *Energy and Buildings* 262 112012
- [8] Chain C 2004 Caractérisation spectrale et directionnelle de la lumière naturelle: application à l'éclairage des bâtiments These de doctorat (Lyon, INSA)
- [9] Diakite-Kortlever A and Knoop M 2021 Forecast accuracy of existing luminance-related spectral sky models ...*Lighting Research & Technology* 53 657–76
- [10] Solemma LLC, Alertness CRC. ALFA - Adaptive Lighting for Alertness. 2018
- [11] B. Mayer and A. Kylling. Technical note: The libRadtran software package for radiative transfer calculations - description and examples of use. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.*, 5: 1855-1877, 2005
- [12] Hernández-Andrés J, Romero J, Nieves J L and Lee R L 2001 Color and spectral analysis of daylight in southern Europe *J. Opt. Soc. Am. A, JOSAA* 18 1325–35
- [13] Dixon E R 1978 Spectral distribution of Australian daylight *J. Opt. Soc. Am., JOSA* 68 437–50
- [14] Kok C J 1972 Spectral irradiance of daylight at Pretoria *J. Phys. D: Appl. Phys.* 5 1513–20
- [15] Diakite-Kortlever A, Weber N and Knoop M 2023 Reconstruction of Daylight Spectral Power Distribution Based on Correlated Color Temperature ... *LEUKOS* 19 118–45
- [16] Petty, G. W. (2008). *A first course in atmospheric thermodynamics*. Sundog Publishing., 472 p
- [17] Anderson G P, Clough S A, Kneizys F X, Chetwynd J H and Shettle E P 1986 AFGL atmospheric constituent profiles
- [18] Shettle E P 1990 Models of aerosols, clouds, and precipitation for atmospheric propagation studies In AGARD
- [19] Stammes K, Tsay S-C, Wiscombe W and Jayaweera K 1988 Numerically stable algorithm for discrete-ordinate-method radiative transfer in multiple scattering and emitting layered media *Appl. Opt.* 27 2502
- [20] Kurucz R L 1994 Synthetic Infrared Spectra 154 523
- [21] Robertson A R 1968 Computation of Correlated Color Temperature and Distribution Temperature *J. Opt. Soc. Am., JOSA* 58 1528–35
- [22] CIE S 026/E:2018 CIE System for Metrology of Optical Radiation for ipRGC-Influenced Responses to Light (International Commission on Illumination (CIE))